

HEMOLYTIC ANEMIA, PANHYPOPITUITARISM AND RENAL FAILURE AFTER POSTPARTUM UTERINE ARTERY RUPTURE

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ABSTRACT Introduction: After severe postpartum bleeding; pituitary hypoperfusion may cause Sheehan's syndrome (SS), renal hypoperfusion may cause kidney injury, and postpartum infections may trigger hemolysis. **Case report:** We report a thirty years old patient of hemolytic anaemia, Sheehan syndrome and renal failure after postpartum spontaneous uterine artery rupture and infectious process. **Discussion:** After adequate intensive care, supportive therapies, antibiotherapy and plasmapheresis life-threatening status regressed.

KEYWORDS Postpartum bleeding, panhypopituitarism, renal failure, microangiopathic hemolytic anaemia.

Introduction

Sheehan's syndrome may be a result of pituitary hypoperfusion due to severe postpartum bleeding. SS generally presents with anterior pituitary dysfunction with varying severity [1,2]. Association between bacterial infection and hemolysis has been known for a long time [3,4]. Prerenal kidney failure occurs in conditions including intravascular volume depletion such as severe bleeding, compromised cardiac output, hypotension or hepatorenal syndrome [5]. Here, we report a case of hemolytic anaemia, Sheehan syndrome and renal failure after postpartum spontaneous uterine artery rupture.

Case report

Cesarean delivery was planned as a delivery modality for 30-year-old patient for her second pregnancy and, erythrocyte suspension transfusion was performed due to anaemia before the procedure, and cardiac arrest and shock developed due to spontaneous uterine artery rupture 12 hours after uncomplicated delivery.

Figure 1: Cranial MR image of the patient.

The patient's cardiac activity returned after cardiopulmonary resuscitation, and a 15 cm hematoma was detected in the abdominopelvic region. Due to the progression of the patient's deep anaemia (Hb: 2.4 g/ dl) and thrombocytopenia (Plt: 40.000 / mm³) despite transfusion, she was re-operated for active bleeding, and total abdominal hysterectomy was performed and followed in the intensive care unit with intubation and mechanical ventilation requirements. After clinical, peripheral smear and laboratory evaluations because of anemia and thrombocytopenia, hemolytic anemia was suspected and erythrocyte suspension, platelet and TDP replacement were performed. (Hb: 5.7 gr/ dl, Hct: %16.7, Plt: 63000/ mm³, APTT: 246, PT: 28, INR: 2.75, AST: 4202 U/ ml, ALT: 1928 U/ ml, Amylase: 1978 U/ ml, Lipase: 419 U / ml, LDH: 6000 U/ ml , Urea: 76 mg/ dl, Creatinine: 4.1 mg/ dl, Na: 147 mg/ dl, N: 4.3 mg/ dl). Plasmapheresis was

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DOI:10.5455/IJMRCR.hemolytic-anemia-uterine-rupture

First Received: October 28, 2019

Accepted: November 11, 2019

Editor-in-chief: Ivan Inkov (BG)

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performed for 5 days for microangiopathic hemolytic anemia and IVIG treatment was given. Furosemide infusion was started in the patient who had an oligoanuric course, and dialysis treatment was started in the patient who had no urine output in the follow-up.

Liver enzyme elevation was evaluated in favour of ischemic hepatitis. The patient developed gastrointestinal tract haemorrhage and endoscopy was performed. Stress ulcer was detected, and medical treatment was given.

During the follow-up period, hyponatremia and hypoglycemia were evaluated for panhypopituitarism (Sheehan syndrome) and; thyroid hormone and glucocorticoid replacement treatments were initiated (Initial: Glucose: 72 mg/ dl, Na: 128 mg/ dl, TSH: 1.15 U, fT4: 0.41 U, FSH: 0.57 U, LH: 0.5 U, PRL: 14 U, Cortisol: 5.6 U, Somatomedin-C: 137 U, ACTH: 35 U; Post-replacement: TSH: 1.78 U, fT4: 1.1, FSH: 9.49 U, LH: 6 U, PRL: 21.1 U, E2: 72.1 U, Cortisol: 23.4 U, Somatomedin-C: 153 U).

Leukocytosis detected during follow-up was related to infection, and antibiotherapy was given, while anaemia was evaluated as renal origin after acute phase ESA treatment was given. Clinical and laboratory improvement was observed with treatment. The patient was diagnosed with chronic renal failure and then underwent routine dialysis three times a week. Renal biopsy revealed sclerosis, interstitial fibrosis and tubular atrophy in 50% of the glomeruli. The patient's dialysis and hormone replacement therapies are ongoing, and she is clinically stable.

Discussion

Sheehan's syndrome is ischemic pituitary necrosis occurs after postpartum haemorrhage. Poor clinical course decreased in recent years due to intensive obstetric care and blood transfusion.

In underdeveloped countries, SS is a significant cause of hypopituitarism. In the pathogenesis of SS, increased size of pituitary gland, decreased size of sella, disseminated intravascular coagulation and autoimmunity play role. Lactation failure and discontinuation of menstruation after delivery are the most common symptoms of SS. Hypopituitarism, and GHinsufficiency is the earliest lost hormones. Many patients have empty sella on radiologic screening [1,2]. Hyponatremia and hypoglycemia were evaluated for SS and; thyroid hormone and glucocorticoid replacement treatments were initiated in our patient.

Some infections are characterized by hemolysis, and hemolysis thought to cause susceptibility to bacterial co-infections. Evidence suggests that impairment of immunity may contribute hemolysis [3]. In our patient, hemolytic anaemia was suspected because of anaemia, elevated plasma LDH and indirect bilirubin levels and fragmented erythrocytes on peripheral blood smear.

Firstly, erythrocyte suspension, platelet, TDP replacement and then plasmapheresis and IVIG treatment was given for microangiopathic hemolytic anaemia.

Prerenal acute kidney injury is characterized by decreased renal blood flow due to various causative factors such as severe dehydration, heart failure, sepsis etc ([15]. In our patient, decreased renal perfusion due to excessive bleeding and septic status triggered acute kidney failure. Persistent renal hypoperfusion for days despite therapeutic interventions, the loss of kidney function became permanent.

In women of child-bearing age; pituitary hypoperfusion due to massive haemorrhage, persistent renal damage due to renal hypoperfusion, and the hemolysis due to infection are conditions that should be kept in mind by clinicians and can be life-saving with timely and appropriate management.

Conflict of Interest

There are no conflicts of interest to declare by any of the authors of this study.

Funding

None

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